

Projected changes in seasonal patterns of evaporation and potential evapotranspiration in Ukraine based on regional climate models of Euro-CORDEX project

Larysa Pysarenko¹

¹ Ukrainian Hydrometeorological Institute, Kyiv, Ukraine

Corresponding author: Larysa Pysarenko (larpys@uhmi.org.ua)

Abstract

The paper is dedicated to the evaluation of changes in evaporation and potential evapotranspiration rates over the territory of Ukraine by the middle and the end of the 21st century. The research was conducted based on historical (1991–2020) ERA5 data and modelled output from six regional climate models (RCMs) with 0.11°×0.11° resolution of Euro-CORDEX experiment for RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 for 2021–2050 and 2071–2100. The purpose of research is to investigate possible changes of the outgoing part of the hydrological cycle across the four multiannual calendar seasons relative to the climate normal. During the near future 2021–2050 most shifts in evaporation are expected in winter with increase of 10–20% with the highest variability in the Carpathians and will exacerbate for 2071–2100. In contrast, higher rates in the potential evapotranspiration rates are found by the mid-century for summer and autumn under RCP2.6 and spring under RCP8.5 in the Carpathians for 2071–2100. While the ratio between evaporation and potential evapotranspiration generally demonstrates a steady spatial distribution, a notable exception occurs under RCP8.5 for 2071–2100. During this period, an expanded area with a ratio of 0.4–0.6 for the summer season indicated an increasing gap between available soil moisture and atmospheric demand.

Key words: Climate projections, evaporation, potential evapotranspiration, Ukraine

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1. Introduction

Evaporation (E) and potential evapotranspiration (PET) as outgoing parts of the water balance play a crucial part in the water cycle by linking the hydrosphere, atmosphere and biosphere through land–surface energy exchange. PET is a theoretical parameter that describes the amount of water that would evaporate and transpire if there were unlimited water available in the soil, vegetation and other surfaces. In contrast, evaporation is the actual amount of water transferred into the atmosphere from the surface. The evaluation of such components is essential for implementing reasonable water, drought and agricultural management as well as for selecting appropriate strategic planning (WMO 2025). According to Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (IPCC 2023), the water demand is projected to increase alongside terrestrial evapo-

ration and evapotranspiration rates driven by additional anthropogenic greenhouse gases emissions in the near, mid and far future. Several evaluations of these characteristics have been conducted for different regions for historical period and also for the future periods based on Representative Concentration Scenarios (RCPs) (Chassé et al. 2013; Dezsi et al. 2018; Anwar et al. 2024). Several historical and future datasets have been developed for PET rates over the European domain (Dezsi et al. 2018; Nistor et al. 2022; Bouabdelli et al. 2025) as well as in combination with aridity index on a global scale as both relate to water availability (Spinoni 2017; Zomer et al. 2024). Monthly PET values are projected to rise to 30% and actual evapotranspiration by 40% in some European regions by the middle of the 21st century, compared to the climate normal period of 1961–1990 (Nistor et al. 2022). In addition, actual evaporation from 23 lakes in Europe will increase within 20–40% depending on RCP until the end of the 21st century (La Fuente et al. 2024).

Evapotranspiration and evaporation are rather complex indices, which computations require a lot of input data, depends on selected equations (Zhuravlov et al. 2022) and scenario intensity (Lemaitre-Basset et al. 2022). Additionally, these indices are dependent on local topography, land cover (Nistor et al. 2018), soil characteristics (Krnáčová et al. 2016; Liu 2022) and canopy interception (Or and Lehmann 2019). All these factors influence the water balance of a given territory.

In Ukraine, several studies have examined the role of annual evapotranspiration in forestry (Shvidenko et al. 2017) using the previous climate normal 1961–1990 and the medium-emission scenario A1B. These studies suggest that evapotranspiration rates are projected to increase during the future climate periods by the end of the 21st century. It has shown that for historical period under minimum anthropogenic influence partial deforestation can lead to a decrease in monthly evaporation rates due to a decline in transpiration in Ukraine (Pysarenko and Krakovska 2022).

Due to the projected climate change, a decrease in water discharge and increase in evapotranspiration are expected (Didovets et al. 2020; Osypov et al. 2021). Additionally, in (Bolbot et al. 2022) was found an increase in monthly evapotranspiration during all months of 1991–2020 with the most profound changes in winter up to 37–48% compared to the previous climate normal 1961–1990 over several river basins. It should be noted that during the Russo–Ukrainian war, the Kakhovka dam was destroyed by Russian forces in 2023 resulting in draining of the Kakhovka Reservoir. This event has influenced the components of the water balance and water quality in the southern part of Ukraine (Snizhko et al. 2024; Shumilova 2025).

An annual evapotranspiration growth of approximately 9% was identified over some regions in Ukraine, which may lead to further soil water depletion (Saydak et al. 2024) and affect arable lands. This will require additional irrigation measures as the percentage of land experiencing insufficient moisture conditions are projected to grow (Romashchenko et al. 2020; Lykhovyd 2021). As a consequence, a tendency toward greater aridification has been found when comparing both climate normal of 1961–1990 and 1991–2020, increasing irrigation demands for croplands in Ukraine (Lykhovyd 2021). This is particularly significant given that 68% of its territory was under agriculture (State Statistics of Ukraine 2025) before the Russian invasion.

The aim of this study is to quantitatively estimate projected changes in evaporation and potential evapotranspiration rates for the territory of Ukraine across the seasonal cycle, as a part of outgoing water balance by the end of the 21st century. This analysis will provide conceptual information about changes under RCP-scenarios for the possible economic strategies. It is crucial to analyse intra-annual distribution with a focus on how evaporation and PET values are spatially distributed in winter, spring, summer and autumn. It will enable a more accurate assessment about water availability for agriculture and water resources management under three future climate scenarios RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5.

2. Data and methods

2.1. Theoretical background

Interest in processes of evaporation and PET fluxes has grown in the context of climate change, as many economic sectors are projected to be vulnerable to both extreme weather events and long-term climatic shifts, with some experiencing indirect impacts. According to the IPCC reports (IPCC 2013, 2023) global temperature will continue to rise as a result of greenhouse gases emissions (CO_2 , CH_4 , N_2O) that are long-lasting in the atmosphere. Different levels of greenhouse gas emissions influence radiative forcing, which is the balance between incoming solar radiation absorbed by the Earth and outgoing radiation emitted back into space. An increase in greenhouse gases enhances the trapping of solar radiation, which contributes to the excessive heating of the Earth. Future projections are typically described by three RCPs: RCP2.6 (optimistic), RCP4.5 (moderate), and RCP8.5 (pessimistic). Low-emission RCP2.6 scenario implies that radiative forcing will grow with 3 W/m^2 by 2050 and then slightly decrease to 2.6 W/m^2 by 2100. Whereas, according to the medium-emission RCP4.5 and high-emission RCP8.5 scenarios, radiative forcing values will rise to 4.5 W/m^2 and 8.5 W/m^2 , respectively, by the end of the 21st century (Moss et al. 2010; IPCC 2013, 2023; Glossary 2023). That, in turn, will lead to a different growth rate of global mean surface temperature rates. For RCP2.6 this implies growth below 2°C and near 4°C for RCP8.5 by the end of the 21st century in the relation to 1986–2005 (IPCC 2014). According to (Wilson et al. 2021) in Ukraine mean surface temperature is projected to increase on average 2.1°C and 2.9°C respectively under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 by 2050 and 2.6°C and 4.8°C by 2100.

2.2. Study area

Ukraine is located in the Eastern Europe within coordinates $45\text{--}52^\circ\text{N}$ and $22\text{--}40^\circ\text{E}$. Mean air temperature ranges from -2.7°C in January to $+21.3^\circ\text{C}$ in July with precipitation totals $650\text{--}700 \text{ mm}$ in the north, with higher values in the mountainous regions, and approximately 400 mm in the south (Climate of Ukraine 2003; CGO 2025). Most of its territory which lies within the East European Plain, consists of plains and uplands with about 68% used for agriculture and only 17% covered by forests before the full-scale Russian invasion (State Statistics of Ukraine 2025). Currently, approximately 20% of Ukraine's territo-

ry is either mined or under Russian occupation (State Audit Office of Ukraine 2025). Ukraine also has two mountainous regions: the Carpathians in the western part of the country with the highest peak Hoverla (2061 m) and the Crimean Mountains with the top Roman-Kosh (1545 m) in the south on the Crimean Peninsula. The country has access to the Black and Azov Seas and contains the Dnipro reservoir cascade which includes water catchments such as Kyiv, Kaniv, Kremenchuk, Dnipro and Kakhovka. The Kakhovka Reservoir was discharged due to the destruction of the dam because of Russian attacks in summer 2023 (Snizhko et al. 2024; Shumilova 2025).

According to the Köppen-Geiger classification, the territory of Ukraine belongs to the temperate climate zone and includes several subtypes (Beck et al. 2018; NOAA 2023). Dfb and Dfa—humid with warm and hot summers, respectively that cover most of the country. The southern part of Ukraine falls under the BSk subtype, a mid-latitude cold steppe with a semi-arid climate, characterized by evaporation exceeding precipitation totals and elevated PET. This region experiences water scarcity and therefore requires additional irrigation.

The analysis has been performed for main physico-geographical regions such as Polissia, Forest-steppe, Steppe and mountainous regions the Carpathians and Crimea that is presented in Fig. 1. Polissia is a zone with excess moisture conditions that covers the northern part of Ukraine, Forest-steppe exhibits more balanced humidity, while the Steppe is characterized by higher evaporation and water scarcity (Climate of Ukraine 2003).

Figure 1. Physico-geographical regions of Ukraine.

2.3. Methodology

For the purpose of this research the historical data of evaporation and PET has been analysed from the ERA5 reanalysis with horizontal step $0.25^{\circ} \times 0.25^{\circ}$ retrieved from Copernicus Climate Change Service, Climate Data Store (Hersbach et al. 2023) in NetCDF format for the period equals to climate normal 1991–2020. The ERA5 evaporation data includes not only water evaporated from soil and water bodies, but also a simplified model of transpiration from vegetation. For the future climate projections six regional climate models (hereafter RCMs) of the Euro-CORDEX project (EURO-CORDEX community 2021) were selected to have identical ensemble for comparison changes in evaporation and PET that are given in the Table 1 below. The Euro-CORDEX initiative was developed with the aim of delivering simulated climate dataset on a regional scale under RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 mainly with horizontal resolution $0.11^{\circ} \times 0.11^{\circ}$, focusing on the European region (Moss et al. 2010; Jacob et al. 2014, 2020; EURO-CORDEX community 2021; Vautard et al. 2021). Such numerical climate models have been developed in different institutes, and their detailed description can be found in the papers (Collins et al. 2011; Jones et al. 2011; Bentsen et al. 2013; Dufresne et al. 2013; Giorgetta et al. 2013; Iversen et al. 2013; Voltaire et al. 2013; EC-Earth Steering Group 2014). All of them share the same downscaling RCM SMHI-RCA4 (Strandberg et al. 2015; Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute 2017).

Data of six RCMs for 1991–2020 and were obtained in NetCDF format from (Earth System Grid Federation 2025) that consist daily evaporation and PET fluxes given in $\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2 / \text{s}$ and then converted to mm. Climate Data Operators (CDO) (Schulzweida 2023) and Python scripts were used for data processing.

Both historical and simulated data on evaporation and PET was regridded in the unified spatial resolution with step $0.11^{\circ} \times 0.11^{\circ}$ for further bias correction and calculation of relative changes to estimate future values of evaporation and PET due to possible climate change.

To reduce possible biases, the quantile mapping approach (Panofsky and Brier 1968) was applied to correct models' simulations of evaporation and PET based on the ERA5 reanalysis data. Quantile mapping is a technique that is used to correct systematic biases in model outputs by aligning them with the reference ERA5 data. Seasonal accumulations of evaporation and PET were calculated for winter, spring, summer and autumn. For each season, 30-year mean sums in mm were derived for the historical climate normal 1991–2020 using the ERA5 dataset and for six RCMs for the future 30-year periods 2021–2050 and 2071–2100 under RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. In the next step, the difference between rates of evaporation/potential evapotranspiration (E/PET) was found via subtraction historical ones from future modelled output. The resulting values were then divided by the climatological E/PET to obtain the relative changes expressed as percentages (%).

Additionally, we researched the E/PET ratio that indicates the degree of water availability. This ratio varies between 0 and 1: values approaching 1 indicate that water is sufficient, whereas values near 0 reflect water limitation. An ensemble mean was applied for six RCMs to smooth out simulated biases.

Obtained results from the ERA5 and ensemble of the six RCMs were analysed for physico-geographical zones such as Polissia, Forest-steppe, Steppe, the Carpathians and the Crimean Mountains, Transcarpathia as well as, in certain cases, for large water reservoirs and along the marine coastal areas.

Table 1. A list of Regional Climate Models.

	Model	Realization	Institute	Resolution
1	NCC–NorESM1–M_SMHI–RCA4_v1	r1i1p1	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI), Sweden	0.11°×0.11°
2	MOHC–HadGEM2–ES_SMHI–RCA4_v1	r1i1p1	Met Office Hadley Centre (MOHC), UK	0.11°×0.11°
3	CNRM–CERFACS–CNRM–CM5_SMHI–RCA4_v1	r1i1p1	National Centre for Meteorological Research and Centre (CNRM), France	0.11°×0.11°
4	ICHEC–EC–EARTH_SMHI–RCA4_v1	r12i1p1	Irish Centre for High-End Computing (ICHEC)	0.11°×0.11°
5	IPSL–IPSL–CM5A–MR_SMHI–RCA4_v1_	r1i1p1	Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace (IPSL), France	0.11°×0.11°
6	MPI–M–MPI–ESM–LR_SMHI–RCA4_v1a	r1i1p1	Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M), Germany	0.11°×0.11°

3. Results

3.1. Historical spatial distribution of evaporation and PET

Before analysing future climate projections, it is essential to first evaluate historical evaporation and PET rates during the climate normal period of 1991–2020 based on the ERA5 data. This research has been conducted for four calendar seasons: winter, spring, summer, and autumn in order to distinguish interannual variability.

Overall, during winter season (Fig. 2A) evaporation rates are within 20 mm across Ukraine, with slightly lower values observed in the northeast. The Ukrainian Carpathians show the lowest evaporation levels, ranging within 7–20 mm due to variations in elevation. Along the southern marine coastline, evaporation rate can exceed 40 mm. This can be explained by higher temperatures, stronger wind speeds due to smooth sea surface and of the inclusion of marine areas within the relatively coarse grid at the land-sea transition.

In spring (Fig. 2B), as temperature increases, evaporation rises significantly across the country, reaching 170–190 mm for most regions in Ukraine. Higher values 200 mm and above appear in some localized areas near seas in the south. The mountainous Carpathians region continues to show relatively low evaporation rates of 160 mm and less. The Crimean Mountains also exhibit lower values.

In summer (Fig. 2C), the spatial distribution of the evaporation rate is rather heterogeneous and changes within 250–290 mm. Notably, higher values appear above the cascade of water reservoirs where evaporation can surpass 300 mm and reach up to 380mm. This is due to specific grids primarily covering water bodies. Additionally, surface moisture loss is elevated in areas adjacent to the Black Sea and Sea of Azov. In general, evaporation in the Carpathians is around 300 mm, corresponding to the areas with the highest forest cover. This also partially aligns with the northern parts of Ukraine (Polissia), which contain significant forested areas. Lower values 200–240 mm are in the Crimea.

With the drop in temperature during autumn (Fig. 2D), evaporation also begins to decline. The spatial distribution is relatively homogeneous across Ukraine, with overall evaporation rates 80–100 mm. Higher values between 100 and 160 mm appear over water reservoirs while even greater values are found in the south near the coastline. In contrast to other seasons the Carpathians are not notable with evaporation values ranging from 90 to 100 mm.

Figure 2. Sums of evaporation (A–winter, B–spring, C–summer, D–autumn) and sums of potential evapotranspiration (E–winter, F–spring, G–summer, H– autumn) given in mm for 1991–2020.

PET is an essential index used to estimate the maximum theoretical water loss from the surface, assuming unlimited water availability in the soil, vegetation, and other sources. Generally, during the winter season totals vary from 20 mm in the northern to 40 mm in the southern regions during winter season for historical period 1991–2020 (Fig. 2E). Larger values over 40 mm are typical for the Eastern Carpathian Foothills, south-west and the Crimea Peninsula.

In spring (Fig. 2F) sums rise within 220–260 mm in the north and north–west, where lower temperatures are accompanied by relatively higher moisture levels compared to the south. In the southern areas, potential evapotranspiration ranges from 280 mm to 300mm, corresponding to a semi–arid climate according to the Köppen-Geiger classification. The minimum PET, 180–200 mm, is in mountainous Carpathians, where humid conditions and lower temperatures prevail.

A similar pattern is observed in summer (Fig. 2G), although with higher evapotranspiration values that are around 340 mm and less in the foothills of the Carpathians and a slightly less, around 300 mm, in high mountain areas. Regarding the general spatial distribution of PET rates, they gradually increase from the north-western regions with 340–400 mm and northern regions with 420–440 mm (Polissia) to eastern and southern regions (Steppe) with values 500–540 mm or more. Maximum rates are observed in the plains of the Crimean Peninsula, reaching up to 590 mm, excluding the Crimean mountainous highlands.

During autumn (Fig. 2H), the general spatial pattern of PET totals follows a more zonal pattern, increasing from the northwest to the south as it does in summer. However, the overall PET values are lower and vary between 100–120 mm in Polissia and 160–200 mm in Steppe area. The Carpathians and Crimean Mountains are characterized by the lowest values, approximately 100 mm and less.

3.2. Future climate projections of evaporation rate by the middle of the 21st century

For the mid-century period 2021–2050, relative change in evaporation values for the winter season is projected to increase by 4–8% (1–2 mm) across most of territory under RCP2.6 (Fig. 3A) compared to the historical period of 1991–2020. However, the Carpathian areas show a mixed signal, with a negative rate of up to -6% (within 0.5 mm) as well as positive evaporation changes of 10–12%. Over some water reservoirs (Kremenchuk), RCM ensemble demonstrated no significant change or even a small decrease. Meanwhile, maximum rates of growth vary from 10 to 20% along narrow coastline of the Sea of Azov. Under the RCP4.5 scenario (Fig. 3B), most of the territory will experience an increase in evaporation rates of 10% to 20% (2–4 mm). The most pronounced changes are projected to occur in the north-eastern and northern areas of Polissia relative to historical climate normal for 1991–2020. Positive but less intensive evaporation changes within 4–12% will be in south (Steppe zone) along the narrow marine coastline. The Carpathians will experience rather patchy changes: there will be a decrease of -20 to -10% (up to -2 mm) in some grids, while in the western slopes or foothills an increase up to 20% will be observed. According to ensembles of six RCMs, above water bodies such as Kyiv and Kremenchuk Reservoirs, there will be decrease up to -10 to -15% (data for Kakhovka have become unreliable after its destruction). Under the RCP8.5 (Fig. 3C), during the winter season, maximum increases in evaporation rate 10–20% are mainly observed in coastal areas near the Azov Sea as well as in western, northern parts of Ukraine and adjacent territories to the Carpathians. For the main territory, the growth is within 6–12% (2–4 mm). Less positive or even negative changes are projected over Kyiv and Kremenchuk Reservoirs.

In the spring season during 2021–2050 evaporation changes are relatively homogeneous, ranging 2–5% (4–8 mm), which is lower than during winter season across all RCPs (Fig. 3D–F). Only small spots in the Carpathians demonstrate higher values of 5–10% (10–16 mm).

Notably, that for the summer season 2021–2050 under the RCP2.6 scenario (Fig. 3G), evaporation fluxes are projected decrease by -5% to -1% (-12 mm to -1 mm) with the exception of the Carpathians and north-western part of Polissia where a slight increase of 0–2% is expected compared to the climate normal

Figure 3. Changes in evaporation (in %) for 2021–2050 in relation to the historical climate normal 1991–2020 during winter (A–C), spring (D–F), summer (G–I) and autumn (J–L) under RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5.

1991–2020. If RCP4.5 (Fig. 3H) is realized, the overall changes in evaporation remain relatively small, within 0–2%. The largest changes of 2–4% (6–10 mm) are projected in the Carpathians and narrow coastline areas near the Black Sea and the Sea of Azov, while most of the Steppe shows a tendency toward slight decreases up to 1%. Under RCP8.5 (Fig. 3I), the estimated rates gradually vary spatially, ranging from positive values of 1–2% (2–6 mm) in the west and north to negative values up to -2% (-5 mm) in the southwestern Steppe. Maximum increases of around 3% are projected for the Carpathians, above Kremenchuk and Kakhovka water catchments (the latter no longer exists due to Russian military actions), and along coastline.

In autumn 2021–2050, for most of the territory of Ukraine, a slight decrease in evaporation of -2% to 0% is expected under RCP2.6 (Fig. 3J). Only in the Carpathians southern Steppe and Crimea are evaporation rates expected to increase by up to 6% (3–7 mm). According to moderate RCP4.5 (Fig. 3K) and high emission RCP8.5 scenarios, the evaporation rate is generally expected to increase, ranging from 1% to 3% (up to 4 mm). Maximum increases of up to 5%

are expected in the eastern part of Steppe and the Crimea for RCP4.5, and in the Carpathians and along the marine coastline for RCP8.5 (Fig. 3L).

3.3. Future climate projections of evaporation rate by the end of the 21st century

During the late-century period 2071–2100 under RCP2.6 (Fig. 4A) evaporation fluxes in winter are expected to increase at a greater rate than during the mid-century, while maintaining a similar spatial pattern of maximum and minimum evaporation areas. The largest rates are projected along the coast Sea of Azov, ranging from 10% to 23%, which closely aligns with mid-century values. In contrast, peak evaporation fluxes in the Carpathians will continue to decrease by up to -13%. Similar pattern up to -5% is expected over large water reservoirs such as Kyiv and Kremenchuk. There is also a slight decline over Kakhovka, although this reservoir no longer exists due to Russian aggression. Overall, the evaporation rates are projected to be 6–8% (1–3 mm) in western parts of Polissia and Forest-steppe and 8–12% (2–4 mm) in the rest of the plain areas. Under RCP4.5 (Fig. 4B), a substantial increase in winter evaporation flux is projected compared to the climate normal, with rates higher than those of the mid-century period 2021–2050. The spatial distribution follows a zonal pattern with higher values in eastern Polissia ranging 24–32% (4–8 mm). Meanwhile, the lowest 8–12% are expected along the marine coastline and across most of Crimea. However, in the Carpathians are projected to experience of both increasing and decreasing evaporation rates. Under RCP8.5 winter evaporation changes (Fig. 4C) will be exacerbated, with maximum increases reaching up to the 90% (up to 8–9 mm) in the Carpathians highlands compared to the climate normal 1991–2020. For the rest of the territory, the spatial zonal structure is similar to the RCP4.5 but with more intense increase. In northern regions the growth will range from 35% to 50% (7–11 mm) in eastern part of Polissia. Moving south, this pace will slow to 11–20% along marine coastline. Large water reservoirs, such as Kremenchuck, may even experience a negative trend in evaporation up to -14%.

For the spring season 2071–2100 under RCP2.6 (Fig. 4D) evaporation is projected to rise slightly by 3–6% (8–10 mm) in relation to 1991–2020. Maximum increases of up to 14% (20 mm) are expected in the Carpathian highlands. In addition, the evaporation flux will strengthen by 6–11% along marine coasts and in Crimea. Under RCP4.5 (Fig. 4E), a slight rise in evaporation rates is also predicted, ranging from 4% to 6% (8–14 mm) overall and 8–21% (up to 32 mm) in the Carpathians, with values increasing with elevation compared to the mid-century period. Under the pessimistic RCP8.5 scenario (Fig. 4F), most of Ukraine, is projected to experience an 8–14% (14–22 mm) increase in spring evaporation rates, which are approximately three times higher than the mid-century levels. The maximum values are expected to reach up to 28% (40 mm) at the mountain's peaks and 10–16% on the slopes of the Carpathians. Elevated evaporation levels are also projected over some water reservoirs, reaching 10–14%.

By the end of the 21st century (2071–2100) under RCP2.6 (Fig. 4G) increases in summer evaporation are predicted in contrast to the mid-century 2021–2050, where a decrease in evaporation flux was observed relative to the 1991–2020 baseline. Overall, across Ukraine increase will be 1–2% (1–5 mm), with

Figure 4. Changes in evaporation (in %) for 2071–2100 in relation to the historical climate normal 1991–2020 during winter (A–C), spring (D–F), summer (G–I) and autumn (J–L) under RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5.

the exception of Crimea, where the evaporation rate is expected to increase by 4–8%, reaching a maximum of 11%. Under RCP4.5 (Fig. 4H), there is a tendency toward small positive changes of up to 2% in the Carpathians, as well as in the north-western and western parts of Polissia and Forest-steppe. However, in the east and southeast negative values are expected to prevail, especially in the Steppe and Crimea, reaching up from -6% to -1% (-10 mm to -1.0 mm). Notably, that over Kremenchuck Reservoir evaporation will increase up to 6% (up to 17 mm). Under RCP8.5 (Fig. 4I) evaporation levels will gradually shift from increases of 2% (8 mm) in Polissia to decreases of -14% (-25 mm) in Crimea while evaporation rates over large water reservoirs will increase. This pattern may be associated with insufficient soil moisture content resulting from prolonged drought periods that are projected under the moderate RCP4.5 and a high-concentration RCP8.5 scenario. This lack of soil moisture will lead to a lower evaporation rate. Positive changes are expected over water reservoirs, coastline areas and in the Carpathians.

For the autumn during the 2071–2100 period, under the RCP2.6 scenario (Fig. 4J), positive changes in evaporation up to 2% (1–3 mm) are expected

compared to the 1991–2020 baseline. This stands with contrast to the mid-century period (2021–2050), where the relative changes were mostly negative. A maximum increase of up to 7% (6 mm) will be observed in the Carpathians, while decreases of up to 4% are projected in Transcarpathia. Under moderate RCP4.5 (Fig. 4K) higher evaporation fluxes will be expected along the marine coastline ranging from 4% to 12% (8–20 mm). Meanwhile the western and central parts of Ukraine will not experience significant changes. Whereas, in the Carpathians, Steppe and eastern parts of Forest-steppe they are expected to range from 1–4%. Under the pessimistic RCP8.5 scenario (Fig. 4L) in autumn season, evaporation is projected to increase up to 4% (4–5 mm). The maximum growth of 5–16% (15 mm) will occur near coast areas and in the Carpathians.

3.4. Future climate projections of PET rate by the middle of the 21st century

In contrast to evaporation, relative changes in PET during the winter season do not demonstrate same rate of increase. However, it should be noted that there is a notable difference in absolute values between evaporation and evapotranspiration.

Under RCP2.6 (Fig. 5A) for 2021–2050 winter PET is projected to range from slightly negative values -1% in the north (central Polissia) and the Carpathians highlands to 4–7% (2–3 mm) in the southern Steppe and along the western and eastern coasts of the Crimea. The spatial distribution of PET for RCP4.5 (Fig. 5B) shows a similar pattern to RCP2.6 with growing changes for winter from the north to the south from 2 to 9% (1–4 mm) in the southern Steppe and southern coast of Crimea. A negative trend of up to -3% is projected only in the Carpathians highlands. Under RCP8.5 (Fig. 5C) changes in evapotranspiration are entirely positive. The PET rate increases from 1–2% in the north-eastern parts of Polissia and Forest-steppe, rising toward the west, south and south-west to values of 4–5% (2 mm).

For the spring season 2021–2050, according to RCP2.6 (Fig. 5D), a positive growth within 2–4% (4–12 mm) is expected across most of the territory of Ukraine for the mid-century period 2021–2050. Nevertheless, in the Carpathians this increase will be more intense with rates of up to 8% (16 mm), which may be linked to a higher percentage of forest cover. Under RCP4.5 (Fig. 5E) similarly intense changes in PET are projected in the Carpathians. It should be noted the spatial changes in PET are relatively homogeneous—2–4%, with a zonal distribution and slightly higher values in the north. The same growth of PET is projected for pessimistic RCP8.5 (Fig. 5F) though without clear zonal pattern. The most profound changes, ranging from 4–8% (8–16 mm), are expected in the Carpathians.

For the summer season 2021–2050, PET under RCP2.6 (Fig. 5G) demonstrates growth of 3 to 6% (12–28 mm) with rates increasing from the west to the east of Ukraine. In the case of the moderate RCP4.5 scenario (Fig. 5H), these rates are lower, within values 1–3% (2–18 mm) with a maximum of 4% in the Carpathian highlands. For the high-emission RCP8.5 scenario (Fig. 5I), PET the PET flux in summer increases from the northwest (positive changes are around 1%) to the southeast (reaching 4% that correspond to 20–26 mm).

For the autumn season during the period 2021–2050, changes are projected to be around 4–6% (8–10 mm) under RCP2.6 (Fig. 5J), whereas no signifi-

cant changes are expected under RCP4.5 (Fig. 5K) or slight decrease in some regions. RCP8.5 (Fig. 5L) results show an intermediate rate between RCP2.6 and RCP4.5 within 1-4% (1–8 mm), rising from northwest to southeast. The north-western part of Polissia is projected to have no significant changes.

Figure 5. Changes in potential evapotranspiration (PET, in %) for 2021–2050 in relation to the historical climate normal 1991–2020 during winter (A–C), spring (D–F), summer (G–I) and autumn (J–L) under RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5.

3.5. Future climate projections of PET rate by the end of the 21st century

In winter, for the last 30-year period 2071–2100 of the 21st century, under RCP2.6 (Fig. 6A), no clear trend in PET change is indicated over north-western and western regions (parts of Polissia and Forest-steppe) for the winter season. Simultaneously, there is more intense negative rate, with values of -3 to -2% in the Carpathians highlands compared to the 1991–2020 climatological normal. PET fluxes are likely to intensify from the west to east and south, with changes of 2–4% (within 2 mm) with maximum values up to 8% in the eastern coast of the Crimean Peninsula. If the RCP4.5 pathway (Fig. 6B) is followed, PET is projected to continue increasing relative to the climate normal, further

intensifying compared to the mid-century winter values. At the same time, a negative trend will persist in the Carpathians as for the winter 2021–2050 ranging from 0% in the foothills to a decrease of up to -5% (-2 mm) at the mountain tops. Across the territory of Ukraine, PET rates increase from around 5% in the north (Polissia and the eastern parts of the Forest-steppe and Steppe) toward the south, reaching maximum values along the eastern coast of Crimea (up to 6 mm). Under the pessimistic RCP8.5 (Fig. 6C), PET is expected to rise substantially—several times more than the mid-century levels while maintaining the analogous spatial pattern of a general increase from north to south. In western and eastern parts of Polissia values will range between 10% and 12%, which are similar to those projected for the eastern Forest-steppe and Steppe regions. From north to south, fluxes increase to 16–20% reaching the highest rates up to 27% (10–12 mm) in southwestern Steppe and most Crimea. Fluxes over Kyiv and Kremenchuk Reservoirs also exhibit elevated values exceeding 18–20%, while the Carpathians are projected to experience the lowest or even a negative trend up to -4% at the highest elevations.

Figure 6. Changes in potential evapotranspiration (PET, in %) for 2071–2100 in relation to the historical climate normal 1991–2020 during winter (A–C), spring (D–F), summer (G–I) and autumn (J–L) under RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5.

During the spring season for RCP2.6 (Fig. 6D), PET is projected to increase by 4–6% (8–14 mm) in the central, north-eastern, and eastern parts of Polissia, as well as in the Forest-steppe and Steppe regions. A similar pattern is expected in the Carpathians, with increases ranging from 4–6% on the slopes and up to 9% at the mountain tops. For the rest of territory, the increase in PET falls within the 2–4% range compared to the 1991–2020 period. Under RCP4.5 (Fig. 6E), an intensification in the PET rate is expected through the end of the 21st century compared to 1991–2020. Maximum rates of PET are projected in the Carpathians, ranging from 6–12% on slopes to as much as 20% (up to 36 mm) at the mountain peaks. For the plain territory of Ukraine, changes are within 5–10% (12–26 mm) from west to east. The largest changes are expected in the north-eastern and eastern parts of Polissia, Forest-steppe and Steppe. Conversely, the lowest (below 4%), will be observed in certain areas of Crimea. The most pessimistic scenario RCP8.5 (Fig. 6F), exhibits a spatial distribution of PET fluxes similar to that of the moderate RCP4.5 scenario, but with higher intensification. Maximum rates are expected in the Carpathians ranging from 12–14% on the slopes to 30% (57 mm) at the mountain tops. This suggests that the region will be significantly exposed to the consequences of climate change. For the plain part territory of Ukraine PET rate increases from 10–12% (24–26 mm) in the north-western part of Polissia and Forest–Steppe to 14–16% in the eastern part of Ukraine and 10–12% will occur in warmer regions such as the southwestern part of Steppe and Crimea.

In summer, during the 2071–2100 period under RCP2.6 (Fig. 6G), a further growth rate of 1–3% (4–12 mm) relative to the 1991–2020 baseline is expected. It is lower than that for the same scenario in the mid-century 2021–2050 period. In the Carpathians highlands changes will be within 2–4%. In case of RCP4.5 (Fig. 6H), PET rate will amplify during summer in relation to previous mid-century with larger fluxes of 8% (42–50 mm) over the eastern parts of Forest-steppe and Steppe. Lower values are identified in the high mountains in the Carpathians (25 mm). The pessimistic RCP8.5 scenario (Fig. 6I) predicts the continued intensification of PET compared to the preceding mid-century, while maintaining a similar spatial pattern. PET is expected to accelerate most in eastern parts of Polissia, Forest-steppe and Steppe with levels reaching 14–18% and up to 20% (60–100 mm). Similar rates are estimated for the Carpathian highlands. The western and central parts of Polissia and Forest-steppe will be characterized by PET growth within 8–12% (26–56 mm) and by 12–16% in the Steppe.

During the autumn season, by the end of the 21st century 2071–2100, under RCP2.6 (Fig. 6J), PET growth will be insignificant for the most part of Ukraine, except for the Carpathians, where values reach up to 4% (4 mm). Similar increases are expected in the eastern and south regions of Forest-steppe and Steppe. Under RCP4.5 (Fig. 6K), PET flux is projected to rise with higher values in the south-eastern regions reaching 6–8% (6–9 mm) along the Black and Azov Sea coasts. The overall changes over most of Ukraine will be within 4–6%. Compared to the 1991–2020 climate normal and the 2021–2050, autumn PET flux under RCP8.5 (Fig. 6L) is expected to exhibit a notable intensification during the period 2071–2100. Increases range from 8–12% (10–14 mm) in the western and central parts of the Forest-steppe and Steppe to 16–20% (26–32 mm) in the east.

3.6. Ratio between evaporation and PET by the middle and the end of the 21st century

In addition to quantitative evaluation of changes in evaporation and PET under possible different RCP scenarios, it is worthwhile to estimate the E/PET ratio. This ratio represents how close the evaporation flux was during the historical climate normal and will be in the future to the PET rate under conditions of unlimited soil moisture. It serves as indicator of the water sufficiency and the potential drought risk. Moreover, the given ratio can be used as an additional criterion for detecting either sufficient or insufficient moisture conditions.

For the historical climate normal 1991–2020 during the winter season (Fig. 7A), the ratio is 0.8 and approaches 1 in western parts of Polissia and Forest-steppe. Additionally, E/PET equals or approaches 1.0 along the cascade of water reservoirs (Kremenchuk and Kakhovka) and along the marine coastlines, which is likely related to grid biases at the land–water threshold. In contrast, the minimum ratio of 0.2–0.6 is observed in the Carpathians, likely due to altitudinal zonation. For most of the Ukrainian territory, this ratio is within 0.6–0.8.

The spatial distribution of E/PET for RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 for mid-century 2021–2050 in winter resembles climate normal, though a larger area in the central and western parts of Polissia is covered by an index of 0.8–1.0 (Fig. 7B–D). In the winter season the 2071–2100 period under RCP2.6 is expected to exhibit the spatial distribution similar to that of the mid-century 2021–2050. Under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, areas in western Polissia with E/PET around 1.0 are expected to expand, while in eastern Forest-steppe, E/PET is projected to reach 0.8–1.0. This indicates that, in some locations, evaporation rates will approach PET more closely than under previous historical climatic conditions (Fig. 7E–G).

During the historical climate period of 1991–2020 (Fig. 8A), spring represents a maximum E/PET of 1.0 along the marine coastline, similar to the winter season. However, such values occur only over the Kremenchuk Reservoir and are not typical for the entire cascade. Most of Ukraine exhibits values around 0.6–0.8 with local minimum of 0.5 in the central part. During spring, the Carpathians and Pre-Carpathian regions show E/PET ranging from 0.8 to 1.0, whereas in winter these values are considerably lower at 0.2–0.6.

None of the scenarios (RCP2.6, RCP4.5 or RCP8.5) demonstrate substantial spatial changes in E/PET for the mid-century 2021–2050 (Fig. 8B–D). By the end of the 21st century, under all three scenarios, the ratio is expected to maintain a similar spatial distribution to the 1991–2020 climate normal, but with more areas showing lower E/PET values in the south (Fig. 8E–G).

The summer season of the climate normal 1991–2020 (Fig. 9A) displays a predominantly zonal distribution of E/PET, with values of 0.6–0.8 in Polissia and the western and northern parts of Forest-steppe. Values of 0.4–0.6 are observed across the rest of Forest-steppe and the Steppe, dropping below 0.4 in the Crimean Peninsula. Exceptions include the Carpathians, Transcarpathia, the Kremenchuk Reservoir, and coastal areas of the Black and Azov Seas, where values range from 0.8–1.0. With increasing solar radiation, the ratio E/PET decreases in summer because potential evapotranspiration rises more sharply than actual evaporation, leading to higher water demand.

During 2021–2050, the spatial distribution under RCP scenarios remains consistent with each other, with slight changes are observed only under

Figure 7. Absolute values of ratio E/PET during winter for the historical climate normal 1991–2020 (A), 2021–2050 (B, C, D for RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5) and 2071–2100 (E, F, G for RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5).

Figure 8. Absolute values of ratio E/PET during spring for the historical climate normal 1991–2020 (A), 2021–2050 (B, C, D for RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5) and 2071–2100 (E, F, G for RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5).

RCP2.6, where the 0.4–0.6 zone extends northward. However, in the summer 2071–2100 for RCP2.6 spatial distribution of E/PET ratio will have the similar spatial pattern as for 1991–2020. The E/PET ratio for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 are projected to have almost the same distribution as during the summer season 2021–2050 (Fig. 9C–D). There will be a slight northward expansion of ratio with 0.4–0.6 and localized areas of 1.0 in the Carpathians under RCP4.5 for 2071–2100. On the contrary, under RCP8.5 areas with 0.4–0.6 is projected to extend further north and west. Additionally, values approaching will likely to disappear in the Carpathians. Furthermore, zones with 0.2–0.4 will expand within the Steppe region, indicating that water scarcity could progressively put stress on ecosystems, agriculture and irrigation more in these regions (Fig. 9F–G).

Figure 9. Absolute values of ratio E/PET during summer for the historical climate normal 1991–2020 (A), 2021–2050 (B, C, D for RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5) and 2071–2100 (E, F, G for RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5).

For autumn season 1991–2020 (Fig. 10A), the maximum values of E/PET reach 0.8–1 over large water reservoirs (Kyiv, Kremenchuk, Kakhovka), along the marine coasts and in the highland of the Carpathians. Overall, the ratio varies from 0.4 in the south in Crimea to over 0.8 in the northern and north-western parts of Ukraine, particularly Polissia and western Forest-steppe, as these zones are more humid.

For the most of the RCP scenarios a comparable spatial distribution is expected. The exception will be under the RCP2.6 where E/PET will decrease from 0.8–1.0 to 0.6–0.8 in the western parts of Polissia and Forest-steppe by 2050. Additionally, in the eastern part of Forest-steppe will appear a slight extension of zone with ratio 0.4–0.6 (Fig. 10B–D). By the end of the 21st century changes in ratio E/PET are expected to decrease under RCP8.5, indicating less hu-

Figure 10. Absolute values of ratio E/PET during autumn for the historical climate normal 1991–2020 (A), 2021–2050 (B, C, D for RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5) and 2071–2100 (E, F, G for RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP8.5).

mid conditions with values 0.6–0.8 compared with values above 0.8 observed during 1991–2020 in western Polissia. Similar situation will be expected for the eastern Polissia however, with values 0.4–0.6. Additionally, for RCP8.5 the ratio with value 0.2–0.4 will be expanding in the southern part of Steppe (Fig. 10E–G).

4. Discussion

It should be noted that climate projections are subject to various uncertainties, including the unpredictability of all hypothetical future land use and land cover changes. However, in (Jacob et al. 2020) such changes will be integrated into regional climate models during in the coming years. In (EURO-CORDEX community 2021) was noted that current RCMs do not directly specify possible land use/land cover changes, focusing mostly on greenhouse gas emission scenarios. One of the drawbacks of such modelling is the assumption of the relatively stable landcover extending though the end of the 21st century. Furthermore, due to the Russo-Ukrainian war-related impacts some projected actual evaporation and PET values have become inaccurate for certain areas following the destruction of the Kakhovka Reservoir caused by Russian military actions. The reservoir was completely destroyed, leading to significant alterations in the regional water budget and water quality (Shumilova et al. 2023, 2025; Snizhko et al. 2024). Additionally, it caused changes in land cover characteristics. This can result in discrepancies in both regional climate and hydrological models on local and regional scales further complicated by different approaches for evapotranspiration/evaporation calculations (Lemaitre-Basset et al. 2022).

A high-resolution dataset of evapotranspiration, effective precipitation, and water availability was recently developed for Europe for the 1990s, 2020s, and 2050s, with a short analysis presented in (Nistor et al. 2022). The results indicate an increase in monthly PET of up to 30% in some regions compared to the previous 1961–1990 climate normal. Several studies conducted in Ukraine have also demonstrated the increase in annual evapotranspiration (Shvidenko et al. 2017), under the A1B “medium” scenario. Additionally, evapotranspiration is expected to grow over Desna basin under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 relative to 1991–2020 (Osypov et al. 2021). Our research paper similarly demonstrates a general increase in evaporation and evapotranspiration rates. However, for the 2071–2100 under the high-emission RCP8.5 scenario obtained rather discussing results indicating a relative decrease in evaporation rate during the summer season. It could be related to so-called “evaporation paradox”, where rising temperatures may lead to a reduction in evaporation rates. However, in the paper (Liu and Sun 2017) noticed that CMIP5 models that the commonly discussed “pan evaporation paradox” was not accurately simulated and represented by climate models for the period 1961–2000, even after applying bias corrections. It should be considered that evaporation is rather a complex index influenced by numerous parameters. Particularly, in summer soil moisture content may drop significantly in some regions due to temperature increase, reduced or redistributed precipitation and prolonged drought periods. Moreover, this parameter depends on wind speed, solar radiation and thus, cloud cover. For northern regions of Ukraine, it has been found (Osypov et al. 2021) that soil moisture will decrease by 10–20% under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 by the middle of the 21st century. Combined with temperature rise and a decline in precipitation, particularly in the southern regions, (Didovets et al. 2020) this can lead to acute water scarcity. Additionally, an increase in drought frequency is expected, especially during warm period April–October with severe conditions projected for Steppe region (Semenova and Poliovoy 2020; Polevoy et al. 2024). Consequently, these factors may drive a decrease in evaporation rate with combination of precipitation redistribution in some regions during seasons.

5. Conclusions

Projected changes in evaporation and PET across Ukraine are expected to be highly spatially heterogeneous and seasonally variable under all RCP scenarios and time horizons.

For the near future (2021–2050), the most pronounced increases in evaporation are projected for winter, reaching up to 12–20%, depending on the scenario. The highest variability is expected in the Carpathian region, where both positive and negative localized changes of up to $\pm 20\%$ may occur, with negative trends mostly typical for high-altitude areas. Large water reservoirs are also projected to experience negative changes, whereas marine coastal zones show the opposite trend. With the transition to the warm season, after slight positive changes of 2–5% in spring, summer and autumn projections are less consistent: RCP2.6 indicates a slight decrease, while RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 show minor increases. Future changes in PET also vary in intensity and seasonal distribution, with higher rates expected in summer and autumn under RCP2.6 and in spring under RCP8.5. The maximum increase reaches around 8% in the Carpathians during spring.

For the late century (2071–2100), winter evaporation is projected to intensify further, increasing by up to 12% under RCP2.6, 32% under RCP4.5, and 90% under RCP8.5, with the most significant changes in the Carpathians and northern Polissia. All scenarios show a decline in evaporation over large water reservoirs. Spring is expected to have positive trends, whereas summer results remain spatially inconsistent, showing localized increases against a background of regional decreases. By the end of the century, potential evapotranspiration is expected to rise by 2–30%, with the largest increases in central and southern Ukraine.

The evaluation of the E/PET ratio indicates relatively stable spatial patterns across seasons in both time horizons. The most pronounced shift is expected in summer under RCP8.5, marked by an expansion of areas with a 0.4–0.6 ratio, indicating a growing imbalance between actual water availability and atmospheric demand.

In summary, all scenarios show the largest increases in evaporation during winter and spring, especially under RCP8.5. The Carpathians emerge as a particularly sensitive region. Mixed trends were found over water reservoirs. These findings highlight the heterogeneous nature of projected changes and the need for careful consideration in agriculture, irrigation, and water resource management strategies. The identified vulnerability of the Carpathians is especially relevant for future ecosystem management and conservation planning. Additionally, the decrease in the evaporation rate in summer during 2071–2100 under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 may imply insufficient soil moisture during prolonged drought periods, especially in the south, which will further emphasize the tendency toward aridification.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest was declared.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

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Author ORCIDs

Larysa Pysarenko <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2885-0213>

Hanna Pushkar <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3942-7242>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.